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USE OF INDUSTRIAL WASTE HEAT IN HEAT TRANSFER NETWORKS

The Heat Merit Order Tool can be used to assess potential and support integration.

WHEN DOES INDUSTRIAL WASTE HEAT EXTRACTION MAKE SENSE?

If your company generates waste heat, the following options should be examined:

1. Reduction of waste heat by increasing efficiency
2. Internal use of waste heat
3. External use of waste heat in a heat transfer network

In many cases, industrial waste heat extraction can make economic sense, whereby the value of the waste heat depends on:

- the quantity
- the continuity of availability (especially in winter), and
- the temperature

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF SUPPLYING WASTE HEAT TO A HEAT TRANSFER NETWORK?

Increasing local overall energy efficiency

Lower energy costs through revenue from selling waste heat

Connection to local stakeholders

Visibility of sustainable action

Reduction of local CO₂ emissions

THAT SOUNDS PERFECT! WHAT'S NEXT?

Set up an initial meeting with the NEFI team!

Step 1: We analyse your situation.

Step 2: We facilitate the contact with the district heating network / heat transfer network operator and the involvement of other stakeholders.

Step 3: A cost-effective study determines the feasibility and possible next steps of the waste heat project.

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